

IMPROVING THE FRACTURE EFFICIENCY OF HIGH-STRENGTH MATERIALS

The peculiarity of jaw crushers is the different amplitude of jaw oscillation at the height of the crushing chamber. Crushers with simple jaw swing have a minimum amplitude in the upper part of the crushing chamber, near the suspension axis, where the feed material is loaded. This is a significant disadvantage in the crushing of high-strength material, receiving a minimum deformation at the time of the first force loading. Increasing the efficiency of crushing high-strength material can be accomplished by providing an equal application of force load to the material along the entire length of the crushing chamber, increasing the frequency of vibration of the jaws, as well as the uniform movement of the material. Such a mode is realized in a vibrating jaw crusher with an inclined crushing chamber in which the vertical plane passing through the longitudinal axis of symmetry of the working surface of the jaws is located parallel to the axis of jaw suspension.

Vibrating jaw crusher includes a body 1, which also acts as a bottom jaw, an upper jaw 2 mounted by means of a suspension axis 3 in the body 1. The upper jaw 2 is equipped with an inertial vibration exciter 4, and the body 1 is located on vibration-isolating shock absorbers 5. In the set position the upper jaw is held by the elastic element 6, forming the crushing chamber 7.

Vibrating jaw crusher works in the following way: under the action of centrifugal forces of vibration exciters 4 the upper jaw 2 is driven into oscillating motion. The material loaded into the crusher moves along the working surface of the lower jaw (body) to the discharge slot. And the speed of material movement is the same along the entire length of the crushing chamber 7 and depends on the angle of inclination (α) of the working surface. To an insignificant extent, the vibration of the housing 1 also contributes to the movement of the material. As

the angle α decreases, the speed of material transportation decreases, which leads to an increase in the number of impacts on the material during the passage of the crushing chamber.

A-A

In the process of moving to the discharge slot, the material is subjected to periodic impact actions from the side of the upper jaw 2. When the longitudinal axis of symmetry of the working surface of the jaw parallel to the suspension axis 3, the amplitude of oscillations of all points of the working surface of the upper jaw, located along the length of the crushing chamber 7, is the same. Consequently, the same speed of application of load to the material, which allows to provide equal conditions of loading it starting from the loading area and ending with the unloading of the crushed product. This arrangement of the crushing chamber is very effective in the processing of high-strength materials providing the choice of force loading of the material in the process of its crushing.